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Research Article

**RESTORATION OF ROOT VALVE SPARING IN SEVERE
SEGMENTATION OF SOARING AORTA****¹Dr komal Naseer, ²Dr Hina Iftikhar, ³Dr Asim Raza Mir Shah****¹King Edward Medical University, ²Avicenna Medical College & Hospital Lahore, ³Shifa International Hospital Islamabad.****Abstract:**

Objectives: The aims of our research is to study the patients with acute aortic dissection of the ascending aorta and their treatment with re-implantation technique also determine the usefulness and effect of this technique in patient with serious aortic inefficiency before operation.

Methodology: From April 2017 to March 2018 nineteen participant of acute aortic dissection of the ascending aorta (Stanford type A) were suffer from valve sparing aortic root restoration. All patients were under the age of twenty-four to seventy-six-year-old (fifty-one.7±thirteen.2, fifty-eight percent males). For the analysis of disease like, left ventricle ejection fraction and valve inefficiency was studying by the help of Trans esophageal echocardiography. Length of hospitalization, echocardiographic and clinical follow-up, complications and mortality were analyzed.

Results: Twenty-one percent patients were died by other reason not by valve related complexity. In fifteen percent main complexities were seen after operation. The patient stay was nine days in the intensive care unit (ICU) and the mean stay in hospital were sixteen days. The hospital profile of patient was compare after and before operation it showed that ventricle ejection fraction and serious aortic inefficiency were undoubtedly changed ($P<0.05$). The recovered patients were compare with died patient the numerically difference was only seen in cardio pulmonary bypass time ($P=0.04$).

Conclusion: Valve sparing aortic root reconstruction in patients with type A dissection can be performed with acceptable during operation fatality and mournfulness & better results during checkup.

Key Words: Ventricle Ejection, Fraction, Cardiovascular, Valve, Aortic, Acute, Reconstruction.

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INTRODUCTION:

An aortic dissection, most common acute aortic syndrome, the walls of the aorta consist of three layers that give it strength. An aortic dissection, or tear in the aorta, typically occurs when the inner layer of the artery's wall weakens this tear did not allow the blood to flow in the central of layer. A & B dissection is the type's aortic dissection it defined on the position of tear.

Type A dissection— are an emergency and frequently need surgical intervention in A dissection the tear starts from ascending aorta and rise throughout the vessel Type A is consider more critical type and need urgent operation.

Type B dissection— may be recovered without operation by carefully controlling blood pressure. In this case tear is present only in the descending aorta the treatment of Type B is possible by medicine because it is chronic disease.

Ascending aorta type, A is the type of acute dissection it is a limited but life- dangerous illness. Cardiac tamponade and achievable acute aortic nausea needed urgent surgical intervention. There are various operation processes lead aortic complexity. The current process conducts to eliminate the injured part of aorta, while protecting the aortic valve. Valve-sparing operation keep good survival ratio & it helps avoid cardiac action, because in valve sparing operation are no need of anticoagulant therapy & there is no danger of long-term complexity come from implantation of an artificial valve. Valve-sparing aortic root rehabilitation are conduct in two main operative process: Yaqub has been conducted remodeling method in nineteen seventy-eight for it, & David et al has been organized re-implantation method in nineteen eighty-eight for it. The patient who has aortic inefficiency we use re-implantation

technique. To find out this problem we examine conclusion in nineteen participants who suffer from aortic valve re-implantation but differed with regard to the harshness of their before operation aortic inefficiency. The aim of our current research study was determining usefulness & conclusion of the valve-sparing aortic root re-implantation process in patient suffer from serious before operation aortic inefficiency.

METHODOLOGY:

From April 2017 to March 2018, aortic valve sparing method treatment had given to nineteen patients who suffer from acute dissection type A in Mayo Hospital Lahore. Such patient was removing from research that had valve replacement. To examine the disease, we were conducted trans esophageal echocardiography, left ventricle ejection fraction and valve inefficiency. For determining position of valve and left ventricle ejection fraction in all patients we were conducted trans esophageal echocardiography again after surgery.

Valve shape as well as high and low blood pressure was determined in conformity with published criteria. Aortic regurgitation was assessed semi quantitatively as follows: 0: none, I: minimal, II: gentle, III: moderate; or IV: serious. Valve execution, difficulties, and result examination were accounted for as proposed by the rules of the American Association for Thoracic Surgery/Society of Thoracic Surgeons. Performance was surveyed either straightforwardly or in a phone meet with respect to the order of the New York Heart Association (NYHA). Patients' socioeconomics and preoperative clinical information are displayed in Table-I. As found in this table mean period of patients was fifty-one.70±thirteen.20 years and greater part of patients had extreme aortic inefficiency.

Table-I: Patients' Demographics and Preoperative Clinical Data

Data	Number of male (%)	Number of female (%)
Gender(M/F)	Eleven	Eight
History of high BP	Nine	Four
Smoker	Five	Two
Aortic insufficiency		
II (mild)	Two	one
III (moderate)	two	zero
IV (severe)	Eight	Six

Coronary angiography was conducted in ten participants before surgical operation by the help of it coronary artery disease was found in two patients. Heart surgery was conducted in five patients together, in two patient replacements of bicuspid valve & coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) in three patients. Median sternotomy technique was applied during operation. Femoral arterial cannula was treated with cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB). The aortic cusps were examined for serious solidification, which would deem the valve unsalvageable. The re-implantation procedure was done for aortic root reconstruction. The study group patients were studied up to thirteen months, the minimum duration for inspection were three months & maximum up to twenty-eight months. Continuous variables are expressed as mean $\pm$ SD with maximum and minimum. SPSS techniques were used to examine all data. For numerical analysis we were used Mann-Whitney, Chi square, and Spearman's correlation tests. A $P > 0.05$ was treated significant.

RESULTS:

Aortic dissection type A was analysis during operation in all patients. The aortic valve was favorably safeguarded in nineteen participants. Twenty-one percent patients died of unknown complexity. 11.5 percent patients died in operation theater (OT) due to uncontrolled bleeding; one CABG case patient died due to cardiogenic shock after twenty-four hours of surgery; & the 4th patient died due to GI bleeding after twenty-five days of surgery. Serious complexity was seen in fifteen percent patient after surgery; one case of neoplasms infection & two cases of brains complexities. Mean (DHCA) duration was thirty-two minutes, (from thirteen to seventy-two min), three hours and 20 min were the average duration of cardio pulmonary bypass, (from fifty-two to three twenty-five min), & two hour eight min was the average duration for aortic cross clamp, (from twenty to two fifteen min). ICU stay duration was nine days, (from 3 to 100) and length of mean stay time in hospital was sixteen days, (from ten to hundred). Table-II is showed the comparison of clinical profiles of patient before and after operation.

Table-II: Comparison of Pre-Operation and Post-Operation Clinical Profiles of Patients

Variables	Pre operation	Post Operation
Left ventricular ejection fraction*	(Thirty percent - Sixty percent) fifty $\pm$ six.20 $\dagger$	(Thirty percent, fifty five percent) Forty three $\pm$ twelve
Aortic insufficiency*		
0	Zero (Zero %)	Four (eleven.10%)
I	Zero (Zero %)	Two (ten.50%)
II	Three (fifteen.80%)	Nine (forty four.40%)
III	Two (ten.50%)	Three (fiteen.80%)
IV	Fourteen (seventy threee.70%)	Zero (Zero %)
*Statistically significant at level of 0.05. $\dagger$ mean $\pm$ standard deviation		

As seen in this table, the left ventricle ejection fraction and severity of aortic insufficiency were significantly altered ($P < 0.05$). survived patients Compare with those who died presented that alone cardio pulmonary bypass duration had demographically serious difference ($P = 0.04$), but age, sex, left ventricle volumetric fraction, before operation serious of aortic inefficiency, after operation serious of aortic inefficiency, using entire circulatory arrest and aortic cross clamp duration had no serious difference (P less than 0.05 for all variables). The Patients, checkup was continuing up to thirteen months (3-28 months). All participants were divided in NYHA (New York Heart Association) two classes one and two functional classes. In the time of checkup there was no fatality & also eliminate reoperation and to control bleeding we used anticoagulant drugs.

DISCUSSION:

The aims of our research work to study the feasibility of the valve-sparing aortic root re-implantation procedure in participant with serious aortic inefficiency before operation. Results of research clearly determine the usefulness of this procedure. The death ratio of these techniques was only twenty-one percent during hospital stay due to this reason for reconstruction of valve also using this operation technique. Our result closely related Kallenbach et al. research. aortic wall & dissected ascending aorta were replaced with (CVG) composite valve graft that mechanical artificial valve represents good result after surgical treatment on the other hand anticoagulant drugs required for long period after surgery and after replacement of (CVG) also need of thromboembolic events which increase complexity with every year incidence of two–four percent as

noted in the research. These complexities can be eliminating by the use of the valve-pre-serving re-implantation procedure. After formation of endothelial tissue there was no need of anticoagulant drugs. The aims of our research to comparative study of patients either with composite replacement or the valve sparing re-implantation procedure or ascending aortic aneurysm treated. The ratio of bleeding and thromboembolic complexity were decrease in the recent group, moreover after composite replacement there were seriously more events in the first year after operation.

Currently published researches have indicated the usefulness of valve sparing aortic root surgery in acute aortic dissection type A. Composite & supra-commissural replacement related in the Graeter et al research, Yacoub et al specify re-modeling and re-implantation with look to aortic Disorgement and adjacent aortic re-surgery after two years of operation. With less No of patients (seventeen remodeling, five re-implantation), the pair valve-conserving procedure indicated better strength, while supra-commissural replacement demonstrated a minimal trend towards increased re-surgery for secondary Aortic Inefficiency(AI). Eleven patients were recovered with remodeling & nine patients with re-implantation related in the Leyh et al study. Neither critical increase of AI was recorded nor re-surgery was needed for a mean checkup of twenty-six $\pm$ eighteen months in acute type A dissection.15

Reconstructive aortic valve operation is also serious like acute aortic dissection type A remains challenging. Drawn surgery time with development of aortic cross clip and additional human dissemination time is a potential disadvantage for use

of this procedure. In our current study the thirty-two minutes for mean circulatory arrest duration, three hours 20 minutes was mean cardio pulmonary bypass duration and two hours eight minutes was duration for mean aortic cross clamp. Also, a significant involvement with this method in elective cases is needed if application is completed under crisis circumstances. Nonetheless, it would be exceedingly theoretical to connect the drawn out technique duration to our observed twenty-one percent fatality before operation.

survived patients Compare with those who died presented that alone cardio pulmonary bypass duration had demographically serious difference ($P=0.04$), but age, genders, left ventricle volumetric portion, before operation serious of aortic inefficiency, after operation serious of aortic inefficiency, using entire circulatory arrest and aortic cross clamp duration had no serious difference (P less than 0.05 for all variables). Discussion about these results is avoided because of very low sample size (15 vs. 4).

In conclusion, Valve sparing aortic root reconstruction in patients with type A dissection can be performed with acceptable during operation fatality and mournfulness & better results during checkup. Our assessment results indicate better valvular strength without an increased surgical risk. Limited bleeding complexity irecent past operation, no need for anticoagulant drugs along with complete re-part of infected tissue is specifically appealing & perform undeniable benefits to established techniques.

CONCLUSION:

Valve sparing aortic root reconstruction in patients with type A dissection can be performed with acceptable during operation fatality and mournfulness & better results during checkup.

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